

CASE REPORT

CYSTIC HYGROMA

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ABSTRACT

Cystic hygroma also termed as Cystic lymphangioma is a type of lymphangioma. Cystic hygroma is a benign and infiltrative congenital malformation of the lymphatic channels with large macroscopic cystic spaces. The etiology of cystic hygroma is either developmental defect or primary due to multilocular cystic malformation of dilated lymphatic channels. Cystic hygroma is rare congenital anomaly that occurs in the usually found in the posterior triangle of the neck as a large and diffuse swelling. They usually cross the midline, reaching axillary and mediastinum. Location of Cystic hygroma corroborates the complexity and extensiveness of the lymphatic system in the cervical region in comparison to other regions of the body. The cystic hygroma can occur in cervical region (75–90%), axillary region (20%), and inguinal region and rarely at retroperitoneal and thoracic region. They usually appear as solitary lesions. They are usually infiltrative, often separating the planes of fascia and incorporating nerves, muscles, and blood vessels. They are usually painless, freely mobile, compressible, fluctuant, and trans-illuminate to light exposure. The overlying skin on the cystic hygroma is normal.

INTRODUCTION

Cystic hygroma (CH) is a congenital lymphatic malformation affecting the different parts of fetus, mostly in the fetal neck, axilla, thoracoabdominal wall and rarely mediastinal, inguinal and retroperitoneal areas. Etiology of CH is a complete or partial obstruction of the lymphatic system which prevents communication of lymphatics with the venous system and results in formation of cysts. The hygroma describes an endothelial lined mass consisting of small to medium sized lumen containing lymphatic fluid, together with a mixture of loose collagen tissue, adipose tissue and occasionally vascular tissue. The cysts may be unilocular but more often it contains multiple cysts infiltrating the surrounding structures and distorting the local anatomy¹.

An increased volume of flow in the venous system results from the lack of lymphatic drainage which leads to large veins. A complete obstruction in the lymphatic sacs prevents communication with the venous system and

causes lymph fluid to accumulate and dissect into the tissues which leads to CH with septa thus create large multilocular cyst. CH without septa may result from a temporary accumulation of lymphatic fluid due to incomplete obstructions of lymphatic drainage. Increased lymphatic pressure may sometimes overcome the incomplete obstructions, thus explaining the higher spontaneous resolution rate reported with CH without septa.²

Fetal aneuploidy, structural malformations, hydrops fetalis and intrauterine fetal death can be associated with CH. Association of trisomies, cardiac anomalies, Turner syndrome and Noonan syndrome can occur with CH. Congenital fetal CH can be isolated lymphangiomas diagnosed in late second trimester and those which are usually associated with other malformations associated with a poor prognosis and diagnosed early in pregnancy. In the CH with septa the prognosis is considered even worse than in the CH without septa. Axillary CH was rarely reported and diagnosed often in late second trimester³.

CASE REPORT

A primigravida patient came for a routine antenatal scan at gestational age of 13 weeks. Previous antenatal scan of patient at 5 weeks gestational age showed no abnormality. On trans-abdominal scan findings were a single viable foetus with a well-defined anechoic cystic area with few internal septations noted around the foetal neck. It showed no flow on Colour Doppler sonography. Features of hydrops fetalis were also seen like adnominal ascites, pleural effusion, subcutaneous and scalp edema. There was no history of maternal illness or known exposure to any medication during pregnancy.

DISCUSSION

Fetal CH is a rare slow growing benign congenital developmental malformation of lymphatic system with distended fluid-filled spaces typically in the fetal neck region. Embryonic development of the lymphatic system starts at 6 weeks of gestation and later on it combines with the venous system. The inability of combination between venous system and lymphatic system results in CH. Association of CH is seen with various structural malformations including fetal aneuploidy, hydrops fetalis

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and it can lead to intrauterine fetal death. Incidence of cystic hygroma are 1 in 6000 to 1 in 16,000 live births but it is estimated to be much more than this proportion as we don't take into account the abortions (1/875)⁴.

Axillary CH is rarely reported and determined often by sonographically in second trimester. Axillo-thoracic CH may be diagnosed during routine antenatal ultrasound follow-up. These are simple or multicystic structured masses, anechoic with thin septa and they may contain solid components. Usually, on Doppler examination, vascular flow isn't appreciated. Further imaging with MRI can be done for tumour extension and to determine the characteristics of the tissue. Axillary lymphangiomas account for approximately 10% of all lymphangiomas. Out of them only a few cases have been reported as diagnosed antenatally. A few cases of axillary lymphangioma causing shoulder dystocia have been diagnosed and reported after delivery. USG is the mostly commonly used diagnostic method especially for antenatal diagnosis of cervical CH. Computed tomography is not used due to harmful teratogenic effect of its ionizing radiation on mother and foetus. For further imaging MRI can be used for the anatomy and to see the extension of the tumour⁵.

CONCLUSION

Cystic hygroma is a benign and infiltrative congenital malformation of the lymphatic channels. Hydrops fetalis with cystic hygroma in the second trimester has been associated with adverse outcome of foetus. Care must be taken in the fetus for early diagnosis of cystic hygroma so that counselling of patient can be done and early termination of pregnancy can be performed if the patient desires. This case is an uncommon case of Cystic Hygroma with associated features of Hydrops Fetalis. This subtype has a poor prognosis. Early antenatal diagnosis by sonography is important so that counselling of patient can be done and early termination of pregnancy can be performed if the patient desires and if patient wants to continue the pregnancy, then post delivery management based on the severity of the condition can be done.

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Fig 1. Anechoic cystic area around both side of the neck which is extending beyond the lateral limits of the foetus, showing internal septa (A), dilated ventricles (B), ascites (C), Pleural effusion (D).